

Perspective

The nexus of global challenges and global studies: a trans-disciplinary global sustainability science curriculum

Veronika Wittmann¹ · Dieter Meissner²

Received: 6 October 2023 / Accepted: 13 March 2024

Published online: 26 March 2024

© The Author(s) 2024 [OPEN](#)

Abstract

The size and number of global threats to humanity's at least cultural survival on the very small blue planet of Earth is growing. Exponential population growth and additionally exponential growth of all kinds of consumption have led to the planet's limits finally being exceeded in the final quarter of the last century. Meanwhile this growth has already probably generated irreversible changes in the world which have brought or will bring the climate very soon beyond "tipping points" leading to "runaway effects", endangering mankind or at least its cultural achievements. Science and education need to provide pathways for survival and the design of a sustainable future, and thereby replace having to deal with short-term and small problems by tackling these global threats. This paper discusses these issues, underlines the significance of global studies and outlines approaches to the design of a trans-disciplinary global sustainability science curriculum.

Keywords Sustainability · Global studies · Climate change · Global risks · Master curriculum · Trans-disciplinarity

1 Introduction

1.1 The aim of this paper

The extent to which humans use energy obtained from burning fossil fuels has reached a dimension that is already changing the planet. This growth is based on an exponentially growing population in addition to exponentially growing consumption and production. The loss of biodiversity is already taking place and is endangering the natural systems of Earth and also those of humanity. This essential problem of humanity is currently discussed as "Climate Change" and is attributed mainly to the burning of fossil fuels, and is thereby perceived as a problem of energy use to be solved by using renewable energy carriers. However, as we have discussed in two previous papers, resolving problems—especially those of global impact—requires sustainable solutions [1] provided by a world society [2]. In this paper we extend our analysis to the development of a master curriculum for educating students to analyze and deal with global challenges beyond the scope of a specialist's viewpoint. For this, a system perspective beginning with a broad analysis of the problem should be the starting point for developing solution options at a local and specialized level (top-down approach). Since

Supplementary Information The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43621-024-00220-7>.

✉ Veronika Wittmann, veronika.wittmann@jku.at | ¹Johannes Kepler University of Linz AT, Linz, Austria. ²AQR eU AT Tallinn University of Technology EE, Wels, Austria.

the authors follow the natural scientist's and engineer's approach—and that of a sociologist—these 2 approaches are demonstrated in full awareness that for a comprehensive view, several other disciplines should also be included such as economics, law and political sciences. Representatives of these fields have been involved in discussions but may be underrepresented in this paper. The presented master's program Global Sustainability aims at a *studium generale* rather than at the education of experts in a specific field.

The discussion about the impact of “sustainability” on University education is strongly influenced by the close to 200 books edited by Walter Leal Filho as the Springer's “World Sustainability Series”. In the description of this series, it is stated that “there is a perceived need to foster integrative approaches, whereby the combination of inputs from various fields may contribute to a better understanding of what sustainability is, and means to people”, very little is found in its as yet more than 50 books why and how this “integrative approach” may change curricula [3]. Also, most papers in these books are written without natural scientists input and deal rather with the non-environmental or non-technical columns of sustainability or even aim at creating sustainability science as a new discipline. A good example is one of the latest, “Educating the Sustainability Leaders of the Future” [4].

In contrast, in this paper we see sustainable development rather as a means or even as a tool for developing strategies to mitigate the threats of global risks or even catastrophic developments we failed to prevent in time. Especially the need to stop our changing of climate before reaching critical tipping points has been delayed already for too long. So, we foresee the need to develop measures to minimize their impact, which will by themselves cause new problems if not designed to be sustainable by themselves. So “really” sustainable solutions, i.e. solutions not by themselves creating new problems to the next generations need to become the new paradigm for all practical sciences. We are convinced, that this will develop only slowly with input from different fields of science. Combining global studies and sustainability science to global sustainability science is here understood as a potential enlightenment for students to develop embedded and holistic perspectives on the globe and its environment in the future.

1.2 General introduction

With the world's population having just reached 8 billion [5] and an ecological footprint approaching two Earths (Global Footprint Network [6], humanity's impact on Earth's geology and ecosystems has become so important that the International Union of Geological Sciences is currently considering calling the present geological epoch *the Anthropocene* [7].

Global Studies is the transdisciplinary study of global macro-processes. As such, researchers working within the Global Studies framework employ transdisciplinary strategies to understand global complexity [8]. Since 2007 there has also been a Global Studies Consortium [9] that functions as a network of graduate programs in Global Studies. The Global Studies Consortium is an international academic association of over 20 institutions of higher learning seeking to “promote and facilitate graduate teaching programs in global studies and to foster cooperation among them.”

There are numerous master's programs on sustainability science as demonstrated by the review by Janne J. Salovaara et al. [10]. Most of these programs do not aim to target global challenges. Sustainability science as mentioned in the article above mainly aims at developing definitions. In this paper, we start by looking at global risks and use the results of sustainability science to develop strategies to deal with these risks in the new master's program. As such, the solution options have to be comprehensive, covering various areas. This calls for a new understanding that can't be covered by single disciplines alone. Our suggestion is to bring academics together and to educate a younger generation to develop a new understanding. The main challenge in humanity's near future resulting from technological developments will be global climate change, one outcome of an exponentially growing number of people in more and more parts of the world burning an exponentially increasing amount of fossil fuels for energy production.

Until the end of the nineteenth century only very few if any environmental, social, political, or technical problems had exceeded state limits. Examples of the global impact of changes in climate (ice ages with glacial eras and interglacial periods) can of course be found in early history both before and during the time modern humans inhabited the world. More than 10,000 years ago dramatic climate changes even led to the extinction of species and to the global diasporas of species. Later, in historic times, several pandemics eradicated large parts of the population. However, man-made global threats only started to appear in the second part of the twentieth century. At this time, two world wars had already been fought and mankind had reacted by founding the United Nations and its institutions. The ideas of Henri Dunant resulted in the establishment of the first international non-governmental organization (INGO), the International Committee of the Red Cross [11] aiming to provide medical help in times of war irrespective of the nationality of the injured person. But it took more than 50 years following Dunant's experience in the Napoleonic Wars before World War I, after which the numerous national relief organizations really started to work together internationally.

2 Materials and methods

This paper is the result of an ongoing discourse among two scientists who are continuously communicating cross-disciplinary on global challenges and sustainability. Both authors have been teaching University courses for many years. DM gave his first scientific talk in 1972 on the "Limits to Growth" [12] and prepared a first energy scenario for Germany in 1979. He designed bachelor's as well as master's degree curricula in Austria, (in 2001) and in Estonia (in 2007).

VW is Associate Professor for Global Studies at the Faculty of Social and Economic Sciences at the Johannes Kepler University Linz (JKU), Austria. She worked at the United Nations (UNDP) in Ecuador in 2002. She has conducted several fields-research in Sub-Saharan Africa. She held the national Austrian leadership for Sustainable Development Goal 17 (Partnerships for the Goals) at Universities and Sustainable Development Goals (UniNEtZ) from 2019 to 2021. Currently VW is representative of JKU at the Global Studies Consortium as well as at Africa-UniNet—Network [13] of all higher education and research institutions in Austria and in all countries of the African continent.

This text (after [1] and [2] our third nexus paper) summarizes the experiences of both authors, demonstrates the different views of social and natural scientists, and puts them in the perspective of recent developments in the field as a basis for a new curriculum developed for institutions of higher education across the globe. The draft for the jointly developed master's program *Global Sustainability* is attached to the article as supplementary material. All materials used are listed in the references given.

3 Results

At the beginning of discussing the results, we want to clearly state that there is no definitive "natural" or "social" science perspective. However due to the training in natural or social sciences academics have a specific angle of view. Both authors consider the differences between a natural scientist's view and a social scientists view on global risks as outlined here to be typical for scientists socialized in either natural or social sciences. We regard this different perspective not as a disadvantage but rather as a constructive starting point for discussion.

3.1 A natural scientist's view on global risks

When humans saw their own small blue planet (the "blue marble") from space in 1972 they should have understood that the world is restricted, and therefore that infinite population growth and use of resources will be limited. Ignoring the limits to growth will lead to collapse, as was shown in the first computer models in a report to the Club of Rome. Using their specially developed computer model "World 3," the "Limits to Growth" [14] study performed in J.W. Forrester's Institute of System Dynamics at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) for the Club of Rome—financed by the German Volkswagenstiftung—demonstrated to a broad public the threat of catastrophic breakdowns before 2100 if these limits were to be further ignored.

Now 54 subsequent reports to the Club of Rome have further explored the impact of ignoring these limits to growth. These have been summarized in the most recent report to the Club of Rome entitled "Limits and Beyond" [15].

3.1.1 The main problem: exponential growth

Exponential growth is growth by percent. This will always be the case in a system which changes in proportion to its actual size. The number of children is proportional to the number of parents. Whenever the number of parents increases, the number of children will likewise increase, but by a greater percentage, and so on.

Since the doubling or bisection of a value is much easier to understand than a certain "rate in %," the one can easily be converted into the other by taking the number 72 into account: divide this number by the growth rate (GR) to get the doubling time DT. Negative growth rate leads to bisection (BT) with $72/GR=BT$ [16]. The key problem of exponential growth is that it will ultimately always create the steepest growth and pass any other (as in linear, quadratic) growth model. Thereby it is the worst enemy of stabilization and sustainability.

3.1.2 Population growth

Fortunately, this exponential population growth, which the elder of this article's authors has been seeing for most of his lifetime, in which the world population has grown from 2.2bn (1954) to now more than 8bn humans – i.e., twice doubling in 68 years corresponding to an average growth rate of $72/34 = 2.1\%$. – has on this side of the millennium finally changed to a linear growth. A further slowing is expected so that the world population might peak at about 10 or 11 billion people in around 2100 [17, 18]. However, this might be too optimistic an assumption since in parts of the world there are still very high population growth rates (Fig. 1).

There is a high correlation between high birth rate (large number of children per family) and extreme poverty [21], so that fighting poverty, one of the main United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)—outlined in SDG 1 –entails a clear need to stabilize populations in Africa and Asia. An even better correlation is obtained when a map of countries' Human Development Indices [22] (see below) is consulted, since here education is also included; another important factor in reducing birth rates. However, all development goals must consider and respect biocapacity constraints. In a recent study, Mathis Wackernagel and colleagues found that “a growing number of people live in countries with both biocapacity deficits and below-average income. Low income thwarts these economies' ability to compete for needed resources on the global market. By 2017, 72% of humanity lived in such countries. This trend not only erodes the possibility of them maintaining progress but also eliminates their chances of eradicating poverty, a situation we call an “ecological poverty trap” [23].

3.1.3 Growth of consumption and use of resources

In addition to the number of people on Earth, their consumption and use of resources is growing exponentially. Both numbers—the number of people on Earth and their consumption per person—must be multiplied rather than added to evaluate their impact. Several economic indicators such as the Primary Energy Consumption, the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), or the production of many goods such as paper, have increased dramatically since the 1950s [23]. Therefore, the pressure on nature and wildlife have increased and have even led to the extinction of more and more species.

3.2 The main global risk indicator: the ecological footprint

The Ecological Footprint is a measure of how much area of biologically productive land and water an average person, a whole population or an activity requires to produce all the resources it consumes and to absorb the waste it generates, using prevailing technology and resource management practices. The Ecological Footprint is usually measured in global

Fig. 1 A world map showing countries by fertility rate. Color code: number of children per family according to the estimates of the CIA World Fact Book's 2016 data [19, 20], licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 Unported license

hectares [23]. Knowing the biocapacity of the planet (currently about 1.5 global ha/person but falling due to population growth, compare Fig. 2) this footprint can also be recalculated to “number of Earths” which represents how many Earths would be required to support humanity in a sustainable way.

Figure 2 shows how this value has developed during the last 60 years, passing the one world limit in 1970. Because of the growing population and growing consumption, the Ecological Footprint measure in hectares per person (red curve) increased from 2.2 in 1961 to 2.8 ha/person in 1980, stabilizing since then. In contrast, the Biocapacity per person, an estimate of the Earth’s production of natural resources and its absorption and filtering of other materials such as carbon dioxide, divided by the number of people sharing these resources, has continuously decreased. Both curves crossed each other around 1970. At this time, the ecological footprint of mankind became larger than one Earth. So, the ecological footprint in ha/person can be converted to the unit “number of Earths” by dividing the footprint in ha/person by the biocapacity (earlier called “carrying capacity”) in ha/person (per Earth) resulting in “number of Earths.”

The main part (worldwide about 60%) of the ecological footprint is the so-called carbon footprint, a measure of how many hectares of area with globally averaged productivity would be needed to take up all the CO₂ produced by burning fossil fuels for energy use. Other components of the footprint are fishing grounds, cropland, built-up land and grazing land. In the case of a country, when the sum of all ecological footprints of its inhabitants exceeds the carrying capacity (the biocapacity) of this country it turns into a debtor, having to import biocapacity, liquidating national ecological assets or emitting CO₂ into the atmosphere, leaving it to future generations to fix the resulting global problems [25] (Fig. 3).

3.3 Human development index

The Human Development Index (HDI) is a statistic composite index to rank countries according to the life expectancy, education, and income of their citizens. A country scores a higher level of HDI when the lifespan is higher, the education level is higher, and the gross national income GNI (PPP) per capita is higher [27].

In combination with the ecological footprint, the HDI can be used for a crude evaluation of the sustainability of a country, the citizens of which should profit from a high development without living outside the limitations of nature. In terms of the discussed indices, both should stay within the biocapacity limits of the Earth. This is shown in Fig. 4. Whereas all countries not exceeding the biocapacity limit of one world except for Uruguay do not (yet) reach a very high HDI, all countries with a very high HDI live beyond the limit of one Earth.

So, the needed development directions are clear: all countries should find themselves in the lower right corner, the earlier the better. A growing world population lowers the upper limit of the target quadrant.

Fig. 2 The Ecological Footprint of mankind and the Biocapacity of the world. In 1970 the Ecological Footprint of mankind became larger than one Earth [24] (see text), licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 Unported license

Global Footprint Network, 2022 National Footprint and Biocapacity Accounts

Fig. 3 Biocapacity creditors (green) and biocapacity debtors (red). In the case of a country, when the sum of all ecological footprints of its inhabitants exceeds the carrying capacity of this country it turns into a debtor, having to import biocapacity, liquidating national ecological assets or emitting CO₂ into the atmosphere, leaving it to future generations to fix the resulting global problems [26], licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 Unported license. Both values, the Ecological Footprint as well as the Biocapacity, vary with the local conditions. So, the Ecological Footprint becomes different for different countries, as shown in Fig. 3. In general, states with a small population density are biocapacity creditors with a biocapacity exceeding the footprint of their inhabitants

3.4 Global risks from a social science point of view

The world is currently experiencing several global threats as outlined below. Global warming caused by human actions is listed in global risk scenarios that demonstrate the interconnectivity of states, companies, civil society organizations and people as well as natural ecosystems on a worldwide scale. At the same time, universal risks also reveal how weak global institutions, including academic teaching and research, have been until now. However, global warming transgresses national borders, just as the radioactive rays of a nuclear catastrophe or the loss of biodiversity do. Global warming impacts all world regions as well as all of humanity: no one remains unaffected by it.

3.4.1 Theoretical framing

In his book "World at Risk", Ulrich Beck [28] pointed out precisely the fact of the emergence of transnational commonalities due to global risks and the inadequacy of conventional social research to be able to adequately record them. Universal threads are demonstrating to social sciences that "methodological nationalism" [29] is a highly outdated scientific approach. Methodological nationalism is due to its focus on the inner side of a given nation-state not adequate to comprehend global risks (transgressing borders of nation-states). Furthermore, methodological nationalism presupposes the basic dualism between national/international and as such stands for the so-called container theory of state and society. On the other hand, methodological cosmopolitanism breaks the basic dualism by analyzing empirically transnational issues (like global risks). In view of the global risks facing all of humanity, traditional social categorizations of class, age, ethnicity, or gender group are becoming irrelevant, and science must turn to methodological cosmopolitanism [29] to address the present societal dynamics and to be able to give an outlook on future developments. One point that inevitably arises in the empirical investigation of the subject of

Sustainability of the world's countries

Fig. 4 Human Development Index (HDI, horizontal axis) versus Ecological Footprint (vertical axis) of the world's countries in 2018. In a just and sustainable world all countries should be found in the lower right quadrant, having a high HDI while keeping their ecological footprint as low as possible. The needed development is indicated by the arrows. Some states are marked by the authors, all countries can be found on the website of the Global Footprint Network [27], licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 Unported license

world society is that a departure from “methodological nationalism” must take place. As such, scholars like Ulrich Beck demand a cosmopolitan social science. Methodological cosmopolitanism not only directs its attention to a centuries-long process of cosmopolitanization, but it also provides an analytical model for dealing with diversity in which the logic of “either-or” is replaced by that of “both-and” [30].

In the twenty-first century, categories of social sciences research are shifting. What is relevant today is that global risks affect all people worldwide beyond strata, age, ethnic or gender group-specific affiliation. Even if there are groups and world regions, for instance in low-income states, that are more vulnerable in global crises; no region and no person remain unaffected. In addition, global warming and its consequences do not care about state borders or stratification: it is a *universal human experience*. The radioactive radiation of an atomic catastrophe, a virus like SARS-CoV-2 or the loss of biodiversity do not respect state borders: they transgress state lines and all of humanity is affected by these global risks. Based on Beck's approach the term ‘global’ can here be interpreted as being just the biggest relevant ‘system’ for sustainability, as one of the reviewers of this paper has put it.

3.4.2 WEF's and authors' risk scenarios

In the following, two global risks maps are portrayed: one presented in the World Economic Forum's “Global Risks Reports” focusing on a human-centered approach, and the other one designated by natural sciences research findings emphasizing the natural world. The annually published “Global Risks Report” by the World Economic Forum [31] has enumerated from 2013 onwards environmental risks as among the Top 5 global risks in terms of likelihood and impact for humanity. This designated map is based on the perception of global threats by various stakeholders such as scientists, entrepreneurs, politicians, journalists, and civil society actors.

The lists prepared by the authors clearly demonstrate priorities resulting from different perspectives on the world. Although the lists are compiled by two individuals, we are convinced that the differences listed here are not accidental, but result from our specific socialisation in different disciplines. Whereas the natural scientist lists only basically “environmental” risks, the social scientist, representing mainly global studies, lists predominantly “geopolitical” risks, following the WEF classification. In discussions it became clear that the disciplinary background represents a different perspective on

risks. Whereas the natural scientist concentrates on the manifestation of problems in nature, the social scientist concentrates instead on realpolitik, human actions, institutions and organizations.. Also, of interest here is that both presented lists do not contain “economic” (as “debt crisis”) or “technological” risks (as “cyber security”) according to WEF [31]. Most probably a co-author from these fields would prepare a different list. As will be discussed below, this is the reason why in the new master’s program scholars with different backgrounds should be involved to create a more holistic view.

3.5 Global studies

Global Studies, initiated at JKU in 2009, was from its beginning driven by two main core understandings. Firstly, by the comprehension that any teaching and research has to be open-minded; as such it has to be undertaken from a global perspective. Secondly, scientific activities have to go beyond disciplinary limitations.

The central foundation for this approach was that numerous global challenges ahead of humanity can only be tackled in a meaningful way by trans-disciplinarity and the open-mindedness of science. Any solo disciplinary effort or research limited to a given national or regional container is no longer sufficient to comprehend issues that are transboundary by nature, and as such affecting all of mankind.

In this respect, the teaching areas of Global Studies at JKU were, from its debut onward, transdisciplinary. The “Lecture Series Global Studies: Interdisciplinary,” taking place regularly every summer term, involved scientists from three faculties at JKU: the socio-economic, the technical, and the juridical faculty. The seminars and lectures offered to Bachelors and Masters students as compulsory elective subjects by Veronika Wittmann and Franz Nuscheler included wide-ranging topics. Students get an education in social models in a global context, i.e., outside the narrow understanding of the equation of state and society. These include approaches of international society [28–30, 32–34], transnational society [35] global society [36], and world society [37–41]. Students are educated on issues of global governance [42] and multilateral cooperation. Additionally, students acquire knowledge about inclusive economic growth and sustainable economic development. As such, the UN system and sustainable development are also aspects of teaching. Sustainability has become an agenda for business and a major label for entrepreneurship around the world. Former United Nations Secretary-General Kofi Annan founded the UN Global Compact [43] because he was aware that global problems are too big to be solved only by states and civil society organizations. In the context of sustainability, topics related to global warming i.e., climate wars [42, 44, 45], global migration and environmental displacement, and questions of human security, are discussed with students. Climate wars are not only a future scenario but are already taking place at present. As such, global warming will jeopardize human security, explicitly in vulnerable world regions. In this respect, climate change is interpreted as a risk multiplier [46]. Furthermore, students are educated about culture and globalization. Global culture issues [47] have been discussed due to globalization processes. In addition, cross-cultural spaces have been created worldwide that are hybrid and dynamic, i.e., a global *mélange* of cultures [48] is recognizable.

For the field of Global Studies research at JKU, the following priorities were set: world society, global governance, sustainable development, global warming and international relations, as well as science diplomacy.

At the international level, Global Studies has by now been institutionalized as a teaching and research area at renowned universities worldwide. Global Studies has already been established internationally as a teaching and research field at renowned universities [49]; members include the London School of Economics, University of California, Shanghai University, Monash University, Lomonosov Moscow State University.

3.6 Sustainability studies

Oxford Languages [50] explains the meaning of sustainability firstly as “the ability to be maintained at a certain rate or level” as in “the sustainability of economic growth,” and only secondly as “avoidance of the depletion of natural resources in order to maintain an ecological balance” as in “the pursuit of global environmental sustainability.” Sustainability can be described as “a societal goal that broadly relates to the ability of people to safely co-exist on Earth over a long time” [51].

Most people (and certainly both authors) probably understand the term as did the Brundtland Commission, the 1983 UN Commission on Environment and Development headed by Gro Harlem Brundtland. It was aiming to unite countries in pursuit of “sustainable development.” In the commission’s 1987 report *Our Common Future* (also known as the “Brundtland Report”), sustainable development was defined as development that “meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” [52].

As the Brundtland Commission insisted, the environment should also include social and political aspects. In most of today’s discussions, economic aspects are also part of the definition, creating a 4-pillar model of sustainability. As will

be discussed below, no classical university discipline with such a wide background exists today, so that academics with specialized backgrounds must work together to address all aspects of global sustainability properly.

3.7 The nexus of global studies and sustainability studies

Generally, science is conducted in order to gain knowledge. Scientific knowledge has to be universally applicable. There are facts affecting both humanity and the planet. In the twenty-first century, the number of global challenges has increased. Sustainability studies as well as global studies as areas of research and teaching are relatively young academic fields. As much as global studies proclaims in its self-description to focus on global issues, sustainability studies look at conditions for sustainability. We clearly do not relate to existing Sustainability Science programs as developed in and limited to social sciences. Sustainability thinking is for us rather a tool in dealing with global challenges than a goal in itself.

The number of global problems is increasing due to the collision between an ever-growing population and its consumption, and the limits of the planet's biosphere; and as such, all solutions must be sustainable. In particular fields, the need to act in a sustainable way existed before, for instance in the case of forest management. A prerequisite for mankind's survival is the respecting of planetary boundaries regarding population size and consumption.

The central problem that exists nowadays is global by nature: too many humans on too small a planet. This fact has led to the appearance of global problems affecting the whole of humanity and the entire planet. Two main consequences are derived from this fact: first that more and more problems are universal and must be coordinated globally, and second that all solution options dealing with these problems must be sustainable.

One common ground of Global Studies and Sustainability Studies is that both deal with *transboundary challenges*. So far Global Studies has dealt with these challenges from a social science and humanities perspective, whereas Sustainability Studies has predominantly been a topic for natural scientists and engineers. The two authors of this article are examples of this too-narrow approach.

In the 1970s the ecological footprint clearly proved that there are too many people on Earth regarding planetary boundaries, as has been shown above (see Fig. 2.) The ozone hole as a human-made problem appeared in the 1970s. Science discovered that humanity generates too much CO₂. That was the first planetary limit humanity reached. The number of global problems increased in the following decades.

3.8 Global sustainability studies

In view of the necessity to foster trans-disciplinary teaching, both authors of the given article developed a draft document for a trans-disciplinary master's program in global sustainability. The basis for the yet-to-be-institutionalized master's program Global Sustainability is embedded in the broader agenda to *rethink science for humanity*. Science, as understood here, is based on the commitment to perceive science as a global public good [53]. The expression *rethink science for humanity* refers to the responsibility of scientists having an ethical dimension. The developed master's program also points to the necessity of focusing on BIG questions, in which global challenges and sustainability are the core of the program and approaches the topic with the understanding that "Problems cannot be solved with the same way of thinking that created them", as Albert Einstein (n.d.) [54] articulated. As much as research is designed to be trans-disciplinary regarding universal risks being caused by global warming, teaching must not be limited to one discipline. Here, the central assumption of this program is the necessity of a holistic view.

Furthermore, the program aims to construct global narratives, based on the understanding of Global Citizenship Education [55]. Science speaks a universal language and scientific relations enable bridges to a sustainable and peaceful future. The overall aim of the developed master's program *Global Sustainability* is to investigate future scenarios to transform the present.

A central statement of the program is that global challenges and environmental risks characterize humanity in the twenty-first century. Global warming is here listed to be the biggest challenge for humanity. Furthermore, the design of the curriculum is based on the understanding that global challenges require global solution options, and sustainability needs global cooperation. Global governance is essential to handle universal catastrophic risks. The goal is to find sustainable solution options; digitalization is a tool to reach that aim.

Multilateral action and joint expertise by scientists will be indispensable in the future. Global solution options—in the light of fact-based scientific expertise—must be generated beyond traditional national and disciplinary borders. The starting point is the generation of scientifically sound answers to global challenges and environmental risks. Shared science as such is designated to be the *blueprint of human progress*.

Global Sustainability as a trans-disciplinary, innovative, and transnational teaching and research field contributes to finding solution options at present by considering a new understanding of the role of science; an understanding of this role that openly faces the challenges of humanity in the face of environmental risks, transnational commonalities, and technological changes. It follows a scientific approach that develops concepts and opens discourses on the social, political, legal, technological, and environmental shaping of the world in the age of universal risks. The world needs a "new enlightenment" [56]. To achieve this humanity needs to leave behind essentialist territorialized "container thinking" in favour of a more systemic approach; one that will require universities to rethink the organization of science and education. To say it pointedly: Humanity needs cosmopolitanism 2.0. The educational aim of the master's program Global Sustainability is to provide an academic university education for students that enables them to understand global challenges and sustainability based on thorough applied trans-disciplinary skills.

Due to the integrated teaching of general, core, and special courses in science, social sciences, and laws—as well as cross-cutting fields such as science diplomacy—the students will acquire synergistic knowledge. The courses will be taught in compact modules integrating lectures and theoretical classes in blocks of just several days duration, also enabling the integration of international visiting students. All courses will be given in English. As such, for (non-native English speaking) students the first two terms involve intensive classes in scientific English. The curriculum will generate adequate value judgment allowing action within cooperation networks, the accepting of responsibilities, the initiation of leadership, and a professional approach to problems while constantly updating one's knowledge and skills.

Entry requirement for this master's program is a Bachelor of Science in Engineering or in Digital Transformation, or a Bachelor of Science or Laws. To enable trans-disciplinary work, the students need to learn the languages of their fellow students. These languages are the topics of the introductory lectures in science and engineering, social sciences, and laws.

The master's program aims to set up a collaboration with researchers. The impact of the Horizon 2020-funded project "Using science for/in diplomacy for addressing global challenges" (S4D4C) [57] is seen here as a potential collaboration partner to foster science and diplomacy connectivity.

Science diplomacy has the potential to play a constructive role in future international cooperation to tackle global environmental challenges [58, 59].

- This goal cannot be achieved by positioning science diplomacy as a soft power that can be used by given states to further their national interests.
- Tackling global environmental challenges is a cosmopolitan ambition and a common interest that requires collective action.
- The necessary measures in the field of science, technology and innovation must be organized with (foreign) policy-makers.

For these trans-bordering efforts, a space for interaction must be created that conforms to certain basic rules. Furthermore, the master's program aims to collaborate with the Geneva Science and Diplomacy Anticipator [60] Foundation, which proclaims to "Use the Future to Build the Present." Additional stakeholders for collaboration with the master's program Global Sustainability are the following: the UN body for assessing the science relating to climate change; the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC); realpolitik, diplomatic academies, UN authorities like the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP); energy supply companies as well as climate councils of municipalities, federal states, and states and climate assemblies including at the global level.

4 Discussion

In this paper, scientists from different disciplines and backgrounds—natural and social sciences—used their academic experience (Fig. 5) to debate global challenges and to jointly develop a curriculum that recognizes sustainability from a global and transdisciplinary perspective. In this section, we discuss tertiary education as a heuristic tool effective to address global challenges and sustainability and highlight perspectives for future teaching scenarios. Hereby, we are aware that there are gaps in knowledge to fully understanding the impacts of transdisciplinary teaching and research on global sustainability.

Generally, global warming as the most important challenge that humanity is facing is often perceived to be solvable by technological innovations alone, i.e., expansion of renewable energy and, if needed, carbon capturing (see i.e., the

Fig. 5 Global risks as prioritized by DM (left) and VW (right) [61]. For the color code see Fig. 6

Global Risks Reports of the WEF [62, 63]. This view of problem solving is shared by many state representatives across the globe. Such a perception is from a scientific point of view completely mistaken. Based on findings by the IPCC it is evident that critical tipping points for the world's climate can only be avoided by stopping the temperature increase before 1.5 K and for this by a reduction of carbon emissions to zero before 2050, with additional carbon removal from the atmosphere. Nevertheless, COP 27-participating heads of states, even of the largest CO₂ emitters, did not even agree on eliminating the burning of fossil fuels [64].

Most of human-induced global risks are a result of industrial revolution; and as such originate from high-income countries. In this respect, the main responsibility for solution options for global risks is linked to these states and they also have to carry the main burden for mitigating these hazards.

There needs to be a shift from a growth-based economic model towards sustainable development. This calls for fundamental transformations of mankind's actions. There is a broad consensus in science [65] concerning the importance of man-made climate change. Asking a broader audience to rank global risks since 2006, the World Economic Forum demonstrates the perceptions of various stakeholders like journalists, politicians et al. As shown in Fig. 6, they also rank global warming as the most important challenge that humanity is facing. This problem (Global Footprint Network 2023) [24] has been well known to scientists since as far back as the 1990s when the CO₂ concentrations in the atmosphere—as have been directly measured since 1958 by Keeling [66]—passed the today-assumed safe level of 350 ppm [67]. Beyond this level, temperatures will rise further with as-yet widely unknown long-term consequences such as sea-level rises of

Fig. 6 World Economic Forum global risks as reported in its Global Risks Report 2022 (WEF 2022) [31], licensed to you under the terms of Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International Public Licence ("CCPL")

up to 50 m (!), as was discussed already in 2010 in detail by David Archer [68]. However, in 2013 global concentrations passed 400 ppm and reached more than 420 ppm in 2023.

A “strategy” to achieve carbon neutrality at least by 2050 is not nearly enough to reach the 1.5 K goal. Additional measures need to be developed and applied as quickly as possible to remove carbon from the atmosphere. None of them have yet been proven to really reduce CO₂ concentrations, whether they are natural measures such as reforestation, planting sea grass, or revitalization of swamps; or technical such as direct air capture and underground sequestration [69].

There needs to be a shift from a growth-based development towards a sustainable world. This calls for fundamental transformations of mankind’s actions. Scientists call for immediate actions since 30 years as they do also in 2022 with their call “World Scientists’ Warning of a Climate Emergency 2022” [70]. The long period of humanity living “beyond the limits” have generated a growing number of additional global problems. These additional risks are a consequence of exceeding the planetary limits.

The presented master’s program Global Sustainability belongs to a *studium generale* rather than to the education of experts in a specific field. As such, it aims to comprehend the global risks and their interconnectedness. In this respect, the given program is unique, because it aims to look at the overall global challenge rather than addressing a specific topic such as the circular economy. In the master’s program *Global Sustainability*, academics are not educating their own successors in a specialized area, which is what is generally done in traditional university education. Here, the idea is to involve experts from various backgrounds who analyse the common topic from their specific point of view. Thereby the students should develop an overall multidimensional and more complete picture. In the proposed master’s plan, specialized scientists teach something that they themselves see only from their specific angle. The holistic picture is developed by the students themselves in the process of studying the transdisciplinary curriculum. There is an exploratory spirit required for scientists when leaving the cosy zone of their familiar discipline; to develop a holistic view by sharing knowledge beyond traditional disciplinary boundaries.

The term global challenge contains the idea that it concerns us all; here in principle this means all disciplines. Furthermore, global challenges cannot be solved by one single discipline. Looking at the terms of sustainability and global studies it is evident that both are genuinely trans-disciplinary. The call for transdisciplinary teaching and research derives from the term sustainable itself.

The central idea in the plan for the master’s program that has been developed is not to put one single traditional discipline at the core of the curriculum. This (uni) disciplinary education was the case in a curriculum developed in 2007 [71]. Here, we place global risks at the centre, and scientists from various disciplines subordinate themselves under this topic.

Scholars must learn to express themselves in the languages of other faculties. Nevertheless, students have to get used to the different terms used in the various faculties and thereby get a broader view. The problem will be looked at from various angles and as such, this will create a new picture in the brains of students. This image should be more holistic than the picture presented by the specialized academics. This point must be further “researched” (as social scientists would express it) or “investigated” (as natural scientists would articulate it) in the future.

In praxis the exact content of the curriculum will depend on available scholars and their topics at a given tertiary education institution, and hopefully will change over time since it should teach the academics as much as their students. Such an evolutionary change should be evaluated by an interdisciplinary leading team and should lead to a continuous improvement.

5 Conclusion

In this overview, we aimed to identify the potential pros and cons of a transdisciplinary curriculum as a tool for university education to address future global risk scenarios for the planet Earth and for a humanity faced with climate change. Our findings demonstrate that by considering future forms of tertiary education, a transdisciplinary curriculum could be better suited to face the human-centered and ecological risks of climate change than a traditional (uni)disciplinary education. Following a holistic and future-orientated approach, where policies and management decisions encourage innovative teaching areas, this transdisciplinary curriculum can be implemented at tertiary education institutions. Considering climate change as a main global risk for humanity and the planet Earth, decision-makers can enable an effective academic policy towards future-oriented research and teaching. Moreover, the curriculum allows for the identification of cooperation among stakeholders of different backgrounds, like business and diplomacy. While the development of this curriculum provides a potential base for policymakers to make more informed decisions on global sustainability, its operationalization will require a high degree of engagement between

stakeholders, including academic decision-makers as well as natural, legal and social scientists. The engagement and contribution of all is essential in order to properly incorporate the curriculum as a modeling framework into the real academic world. This debate constitutes a first attempt to apply transdisciplinarity based on authors' opinions to a curriculum on global sustainability. The global risk of climate change is highly impacting the future of younger generations and requires the development of a diverse set of pathways of future-orientated teaching. Knowledge about global sustainability will be decisive in the future. Further studies should focus on empirically testing the developed curriculum in real-life academic settings later on, as the global risk of climate change continues to impact humanity and Planet Earth on a worldwide scale.

Acknowledgements The authors would like to thank our anonymous reviewers whose comments substantially improved this manuscript. Support by Johannes Kepler Open Access Publishing Fund and the federal state of Upper Austria.

Author contributions V.W. and D.M. wrote the main manuscript text and D.M. prepared Figs. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

Funding Open access funding provided by Johannes Kepler University Linz. This work is based on research supported by the Austrian Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (BMBWF) in the Africa UniNet Research Project "PO74_Ethiopia". DM acknowledges financial support by crystalsol and its support in European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, grant agreements No. 952982 (Custom-Art project).

Data availability We do not analyse or generate any datasets, because our work proceeds within a theoretical approach.

Declarations

Competing interests The authors declare no competing interests.

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

References

1. Wittmann V, Arici E, Meissner D. The nexus of world electricity and global sustainable development. *Energies*. 2021;14:5843. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14185843>.
2. Wittmann V, Meissner D. The nexus of energy for free and world society. *Int J Sustain Energy Dev*. 2019;7:384–91. <https://doi.org/10.20533/ijsed.2046.3707.2019.0046>.
3. Springer Nature: World sustainability series. <https://www.springer.com/series/13384>, Accessed 14 Feb 2024
4. Leal Filho W, Salvia AL, Pallant E, Choate B, Pearce K. *Educating the sustainability leaders of the future*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer; 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-22856-8>.
5. UN. Day of 8 billion. UN. 2021. <https://www.un.org/en/dayof8billion>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
6. Global Footprint Network. Country trends, World, ecological footprint vs biocapacity (gha per person). <https://data.footprintnetwork.org/-/countryTrends?cn=5001&type=BCpc,EFCpc>. 2021; Accessed 12 Sep 2023
7. McKenzie P. Are we in the anthropocene? Geologists could define a new epoch for earth. *Nature*. 2022;613:14–5. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-04428-3>.
8. Steger MB. Transdisciplinarity in globalization research: the global studies framework. In: Rossi I, editor. *Challenges of globalization and prospects for an inter-civilizational world order*. Chams: Springer; 2020. p. 125–38. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-44058-9_8%22.
9. Global Studies Consortium. Mission statement. 2023. <https://globalstudiesconsortium.org/mission-statement/>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
10. Salovaara JJ, Soini K, Pietikäinen J. Sustainability science in education: analysis of master's programmes' curricula. *Sustain Sci*. 2020;15:901–15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-019-00745-1>.
11. ICRC. Founding and early years of the ICRC (1863–1914). 2023. <https://www.icrc.org/en/document/founding-and-early-years-icrc-1863-1914>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
12. Meadows DH, Meadows DL, Randers J, Behrens WWIII. *The Limits to growth: a report for the club of Rome's project on the predicament of mankind*. New York: Potomac Associates; 1972.
13. OeAD. Africa-UniNet: Homepage. 2022. <https://africa-uninet.at/en/>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
14. "Limits to Growth" study performed in J.W. Forrester's Institute of system dynamics at the massachusetts institute of technology (MIT) for the club of Rome—financed by the German Volkswagenstiftung.
15. Bardi U, Alvarez-Pereira C. *Limits and beyond, a report to the club of Rome*. London: Exapt Press; 2022.

16. Slavin S. All the math you'll ever need. Hoboken NJ: Wiley; 1989.
17. Cilluffoneil A, Ruiz G. World's population is projected to nearly stop growing by the end of the century, Pew Research Center. 2019. <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2019/06/17/worlds-population-is-projected-to-nearly-stop-growing-by-the-end-of-the-century/>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
18. UN. World Population Prospects 2019, Highlights, United Nations, New York. 2019. https://population.un.org/wpp/Publications/Files/WPP2019_Highlights.pdf. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
19. CIA. The World Fact Book. CIA. 2016. <https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/about/archives/2021/>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
20. Wikipedia. Population growth. A world map showing global variations in fertility rate per woman according to the CIA World Factbook's 2016 data. 2023. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Population_growth. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
21. Our World in Data. SDG Tracker. 2022. <https://sdg-tracker.org/no-poverty—targets>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
22. United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). Human development index (HDI). UNDP. 2023 <https://hdr.undp.org/data-center/human-development-index#/indicies/HDI>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
23. Wackernagel M, Hanscom L, Jayasinghe P, Lin D, Murthy A, Neill E, Raven P. The importance of resource security for poverty eradication. *Nat Sustain*. 2021;4:731–8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-021-00708-4>.
24. Global Footprint Network. Homepage. 2023. <https://data.footprintnetwork.org/#/>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
25. von Weizsäcker EU. So reicht das nicht. Außenpolitik, neue Ökonomie, neue Aufklärung: Was wir in der Klimakrise jetzt wirklich brauchen. Paderborn: Bonifatius; 2022. p. 72–5.
26. Global Footprint Network. Glossary. 2022. <https://www.footprintnetwork.org/resources/glossary/>—Ecologicalfootprint/. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
27. Global Footprint Network. Measuring Sustainable Development. 2022. <https://www.footprintnetwork.org/our-work/sustainable-development/>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
28. Beck U. World at risk. Cambridge: Polity Press; 2009.
29. Beck U, Sznaider N. Unpacking cosmopolitanism for the social sciences: a research agenda. *Br J Sociol*. 2006;57:1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-4446.2006.00091.x>.
30. Berking H. Globalisierung. In: Baur N, Korte H, Löw M, Schroer M, editors. *Handbuch Soziologie*. 1st ed. Wiesbaden: Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften; 2008. pp 117–137, p 124
31. World Economic Forum. The Global Risks Report 2022. World Geneva: Economic Forum. https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_The_Global_Risks_Report_2022.pdf. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
32. Buzan B. From international to world society? English school theory and the social structure of globalisation. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2004.
33. Buzan B. An introduction to the english school of international relations: the societal approach. Hoboken NJ: John Wiley & Sons; 2014.
34. Bull H, Watson A. The expansion of international society. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 1984.
35. Kaiser K. Transnationale Politik. Zu einer Theorie der multinationalen Politik. In: Czempel EO, ed. *Die anachronistische Souveränität: Zum Verhältnis von Innen- und Außenpolitik*, Politische Vierteljahresschrift, Sonderheft 1, Köln/Opladen: Westdeutscher Verlag; 1969. pp 80–109.
36. Albrow M. The global age: state and society beyond modernity. Cambridge: Polity Press; 1996.
37. Burton JW. World society. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 1972.
38. Luhmann N. Theory of society, cultural memory in the present, vol. 1. Palo Alto CA: Stanford University Press; 2003.
39. Luhmann N. Theory of society, cultural memory in the present, vol. 2. Palo Alto CA: Stanford University Press; 2013.
40. Wittmann V. Weltgesellschaft: rekonstruktion eines wissenschaftlichen Diskurses. Studien zur Politischen Soziologie. Band 27. Baden-Baden: Nomos Verlag; 2014.
41. Wittmann V. Weltgesellschaft. In: Nohlen D, Grotz F, editors. *Kleines Lexikon der Politik*. 6th ed. Beck: München; C.H; 2015. p. 734–6.
42. Kennedy P, Messner D, Nuscheler F. Global trends and global governance. London: Pluto Press; 2001.
43. UN global compact. 20 years of the UN Global Compact. UN. 2022 <https://www.unglobalcompact.org/take-action/20th-anniversary-campaign>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
44. Dyer G. Climate wars: the fight for survival as the world overheats. London: Oneworld Publications; 2011.
45. Welzer H. Climate wars: what people will be killed in the twenty-first century. Cambridge: Polity Press; 2017.
46. WBGU—German advisory council on global change. Climate change as a security risk. Berlin: WBGU; 2007. https://www.wbgu.de/fileadmin/user_upload/wbgu/publikationen/hauptgutachten/hg2007/pdf/wbgu_hg2007_engl.pdf Accessed 20 Feb 2024.
47. Featherstone M. Global culture: nationalism, globalization and modernity. London: Sage Publications; 1992.
48. Pieterse JN. Globalization and culture. Global mélange. 4th ed. New York NY: Rowman & Littlefield; 2019.
49. Global studies consortium. a network of graduate programs in global studies. 2023. <https://globalstudiesconsortium.org/member-programs/>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
50. Oxford languages. Sustainability: meaning. 2023. <https://www.google.at/search?q=sustainability+meaning>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
51. Hirsch M. Sustainability: our goals as a society. Ulprospector. 2022. <https://www.ulprospector.com/knowledge/13480/pc-sustainability-our-goals-as-a-society/>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
52. United nations general assembly. Report of the world commission on environment and development: our common future. transmitted to the general assembly as an annex to document A/42/427—Development and international co-operation: environment. UN. 1987. <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/5987our-common-future.pdf>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
53. Boulton GS. Science as a global public good. International science council position paper. 2021. <https://council.science/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/ScienceAsAPublicGood-FINAL.pdf>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
54. Einstein A, quoted in: WBGU—German advisory council on global change. Towards our common digital future. Summary. Berlin: WBGU; 2019.
55. UNESCO. Global citizenship education. UNESCO. 2023. <https://en.unesco.org/themes/gced>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
56. von Weizsäcker EU, Wijkman A. Come on! capitalism, short-termism: population and the destruction of the planet. 1st ed. Berlin: Springer; 2018.

57. Meyer N. The Impact Story of S4D4C. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant agreement No 770342. 2021. <https://www.s4d4c.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/The-Impact-Story-of-S4D4C.pdf> Accessed 12 Sep 2023
58. Wittmann V, Kinash E. Science diplomacy for environment: global outlooks and green digital diplomacy as a new approach in the EU environmental diplomacy. *Russian Political Sci J*. 2022;24(3):6–14.
59. Wittmann V. Global warming and the concepts of world society: the coincidence of epistemological and political challenges. In: Suter C, Ziltener P, editors. *After globalization: the future of world society*. Zürich: World Society Studies; 2023.
60. Geneva science and diplomacy anticipator. *Vision*. 2023. <https://gesda.global/vision/>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023.
61. Meissner D, Wittmann V. Global Risks as prioritized by Dieter Meissner (left) and by Veronika Wittmann (right). Graphic design by Dieter Meissner, 2023, unpublished.
62. World Economic Forum. The global risks report 2023. World Geneva: economic forum. https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Global_Risks_Report_2023.pdf. Accessed 19 Feb 2024
63. World Economic Forum. The global risks report 2024. World Geneva: economic forum. https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_The_Global_Risks_Report_2024.pdf. Accessed 19 Feb 2024
64. United Nations Environment Programme. COP27 ends with announcement of historic loss and damage fund. UNEP. November 22, 2022. <https://www.unep.org/news-and-stories/story/cop27-ends-announcement-historic-loss-and-damage-fund>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
65. Oreskes N. The scientific consensus on climate change. *Science*. 2004;306:1686. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1103618>.
66. Keeling CD. The keeling curve Charles David keeling started measurements already in 1958 (continued since Charles's death in 2005 by his son Ralph) in the Mauna Loa Observatory on Hawaii. 2022. <https://keelingcurve.ucsd.edu/>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
67. Rockström J, Gaffney O. *Breaking boundaries*. New York NY: DK Publishing; 2021.
68. Archer D. *The long Thaw: how humans are changing the next 100,000 years of earth's climate*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press; 2010.
69. World Resources Institute. Carbon Removal. ERI, 2022. <https://www.wri.org/initiatives/carbon-removal>. Accessed 12 Sep 2023
70. Ripple W, Wolf C, Gregg JW, Levin K, Rockström J, Newsome TM, Betts MG, Huq S, Law BE, Kemp L, Kalmus P, Lenton TM. World scientists' warning of a climate emergency 2022. *Bioscience*. 2022;72:1149–55. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biac083>.
71. Meissner D, Mellikov E, Öpik A, Koppel I, Lust E. A new curriculum in sustainable energetics in Estonia. *J Mat Education*. 2009;31:23–32.

Publisher's Note Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.